

Parvovirus B19 is the cause of acute myeloid leukemia

Ilija Barukčić¹

¹ Internist, Horandstrasse, DE-26441 Jever, Germany

Received: October 9th, 2020. Published: October 9th, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4075205>

Objectives: Pharmacology in the form of a two-phase chemotherapy (induction chemotherapy (cytarabine, anthracycline) and post remission (or consolidation) therapy) and hematopoietic stem cell transplantation are important features of today's acute myeloid leukemia (AML) therapy. Because of the toxic (side) effects of the AML efforts to use other therapeutic strategies (tyrosine kinase inhibitors) in AML continue. Identifying a cause or the cause of AML would be of very valuable knowledge in order to accelerate the transition towards a highly effective and low toxic therapy of the AML.

Methods: The molecular parvovirus B19 study (20 patients with AML and 60 controls) of El-Khier et al. (1) has been re-analysed. Appropriate statistical methods like the necessary condition relationship (2,3), the sufficient condition relationship (4), the necessary and sufficient condition relationship (5) and the causal (6) relationship k were used for causal (7) data analysis. A p-value (8) of less than 0.05 is treated as significant.

Results: *Without* parvovirus B19 infection *no* acute myeloid leukemia (P value = 0.0108). *If* parvovirus B19 infection *then* acute myeloid leukemia. Parvovirus B19 infection *is a necessary and sufficient condition* acute myeloid leukemia. The causal relationship k between a parvovirus B19 infection *and* acute myeloid leukemia is highly significant (k = +0.7866, p Value right tailed = 2.55351E-15).

Conclusions: The data of the study of El-Khier et al. support the alternative hypothesis that *parvovirus B19 is the cause of acute myeloid leukemia* (p Value < 0.001).

References:

- (1) El-Khier NTA, Darwish A, Zaki MES. Molecular Study of Parvovirus B19 Infection in Children with Acute Myeloid Leukemia. *Asian Pac J Cancer Prev*. 2018;19(2):337-342. doi: <https://doi.org/10.22034/APJCP.2018.19.2.337>
- (2) Barukčić K, Barukčić JP, Barukčić I. Epstein-Barr virus is the cause of rheumatoid arthritis. *Romanian journal of rheumatology*. 2018;27(4):148-163. Accessed December 29, 2018. <https://www.mendeley.com/impact/ilija--baruki>
- (3) Barukčić K, Barukčić I. Epstein Barr Virus—The Cause of Multiple Sclerosis. *JAMP*. 2016;04(06):1042-1053. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Ilija_Barukcic2
- (4) Barukčić I. Mycobacterium Avium Subspecies Paratuberculosis. *Modern Health Science*. 2018;1(1):p19-p19. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6988-2780>
- (5) Barukčić I. Human papillomavirus is the cause of human prostate cancer. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*. 2019;9(4-s):577-588.
- (6) Barukčić I. The Mathematical Formula of the Causal Relationship k. *IJAPM*. 2016;6(2):45-65. <https://publons.com/researcher/3501739/ilija-barukcic/>
- (7) Barukčić I. Epstein-Barr virus is the cause of multiple sclerosis. *International Journal of Current Medical and Pharmaceutical Research*. 2018;4(9 (A)):3674–3682.
- (8) Barukčić I. The P Value of likely extreme events. *International Journal of Current Science Research*. 2019;5(11):1841–1861.